

Pinchable Device with Drive Unit for Illusory Pulling Sensations

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Abstract. Illusory pulling sensations were generated by applying asymmetric vibrations to fingertips. Although this illusion can be induced by vibrators that are small enough to be pinched with fingertips, the size of the device used to induce the illusion was increased by the drive unit (power supply and control circuit) for the vibrators. Therefore, a pinchable device with a drive unit for illusory pulling sensation was developed. The device consists of two vibrators, a Li-Po battery, and a control circuit in a housing that can be pinched with the fingertips. A performance evaluation of the device revealed a battery life of approximately 90 minutes. In addition, the participants were able to discriminate a median correct response rate of 93.75% for four directions of illusory forward-backward translation force and clockwise-counterclockwise torque.

Keywords: Illusory pulling sensations · Asymmetric vibration · Pinchable device.

1 Introduction

Illusory pulling sensations are induced by asymmetric vibration stimuli that asymmetrically change accelerations when applied to fingertips [1, 2]. This illusion can be induced by vibrators that are sufficiently small to be pinched with the fingertips and have been applied to pedestrian navigation [3]. However, placing the drive unit, which includes the power supply and control circuit for the vibrators, is challenging. In conventional devices, the vibrator is wired to an external drive unit (external unit-type, Fig.1(a)) [1, 2, 4]. Alternatively, the vibrator floating by springs is connected to a holdable device, including the drive unit (holdable type in Fig.1(a)) [3, 5, 6]. The mechanism of holdable type device can also generate a physical force between the area pinched by the fingertips and the gripped drive unit, which acts as the grounding point. In other words, because this type can present directional cues through physical forces instead of asymmetric vibration stimuli, the advantage of the illusory pulling sensation, which presents cues by only pinching the vibrator, could not be demonstrated. In this study, we developed a pinchable device with the drive unit for illusory pulling sensations, taking on the engineering challenge to leverage this illusion (pinchable type in Fig.1(a)).

2 Configuration of Pinchable Device

The pinchable device consists of two vibrators (639897, Foster Electric Co., Ltd.), a control circuit, and a Li-Po battery (400 mAh, DTP502535, Data Power Technology

Fig. 1. Pinchable device. (a) Comparison with conventional devices. (b) Internal configuration diagram of the device. (c) Overview (size: 52.8(w)×46.0(h)×30.0(d) mm, weight: 88.6 g). (d) Control circuit. (e) Typical example of the asymmetric vibration stimuli (dot line: target, and solid line: measured). (f) Stimulus–Response confusion matrix.

Ltd.) (Fig.1(b)). These components were built into a 3D-printed acrylic housing, and the device was sufficiently large and heavy to be pinched with the thumb, index, and middle fingers (Fig. 1(c)). By placing two-channel vibrators in parallel and changing the combination of the illusory force vectors presented by both vibrators, the sensations of translational force (forward–backward) and torque (clockwise (CW)–counterclockwise (CCW)) can be induced [4]. Based on this finding, illusory pulling sensations were induced in four directions by the pinchable device.

Asymmetric vibration stimuli can be controlled by audio signals because the principle of voice-coil-type vibrators is similar to that of acoustic speakers. A Bluetooth audio module (BM83SM1-00AA, Microchip Technology, Inc.) was used to transmit the control signal from the information terminal to the vibrator (Fig.1(d)). This module allows the device to connect wirelessly to various information terminals such as smartphones and tablets as quickly as a Bluetooth headset. For the asymmetric vibration stimulation, the waveform in Eq. (1) developed by the author’s group was used [7].

$$\ddot{x}_{ref}(t) = A_1 \sin(2\pi ft) + A_2 \sin(4\pi ft + \phi_0) \quad (1)$$

The vibration stimulus was calibrated based on the frequency response of the device (Fig. 1 (e)), and the control signals were generated as audio signals in WAV file format. Refer to Tanabe et al. [7] for the calibration method.

3 Performance Evaluation

First, the basic specifications of the devices were investigated. Although the size and weight of the device increased because of the built-in drive unit, it was confirmed that the target vibration could be generated (Fig. 1 (e)). The battery life was actually measured when the vibrators were turned on and off in 1-second cycles at the maximum output. Consequently, the drive lasted for approximately 90 minutes, and the outputted acceleration decreased by 0.19% per minute.

Next, we evaluated whether participants could discriminate the direction of the illusion. Five participants aged 31–59 years (one female) participated in the experiment. This study was approved by the Institutional Review Board of the National Institute of Advanced Industrial Science and Technology (approval number: HF2019-0966-B). Forward and backward translational forces, and clockwise and counterclockwise torques for 1 s were randomly presented to the participants for 20 trials in each direction. Participants responded to the perceived direction using a four-alternative forced choice. Correct response rates were calculated for each direction. The results showed a median correct response rate of 93.75% with an interquartile range of 11.56% (Fig. 1(f)). In addition, the median correct response rate for each direction was 100% for forward and backward and 95% for CW and CCW. Although the preliminary experimental results were obtained with a small sample size, these correct response rates were comparable to those of the conventional external unit type [4] and holdable type [3].

Disclosure of Interests. The author has no competing interests to declare that are relevant to the content of this article.

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